

JURISPRUDENCE

SURETYSHIP AS A MEANS OF SECURING A CLAIM (COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS)

Ekaterine Ninua

*Associate Professor of Law Department, Faculty of Business, Law and Social Sciences
Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi, Georgia*

Tamila Khurtsidze

*Associate Professor of Law Department, Faculty of Business, Law and Social Sciences
Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi, Georgia*

Abstract

The scientific paper Suretyship as a Means of Securing a Demand (Comparative Legal Analysis) deals with the concept of the institution of suretyship and its content on the example of the legislation of both Georgian and foreign countries. Based on the above research, the important role of suretyship as an institution in legal relations was revealed, since, due to the development of credit relations in financial institutions, the role of suretyship as a personal guarantee of the fulfillment of obligations is becoming more relevant day by day, which is due to the fact that banks and microfinance organizations no longer conclude loan agreements without collateral. Based on the civil legislation of foreign countries, the similarities and differences that characterize the institution of suretyship in legal relations were identified. In addition, the paper expresses the author's opinion that guarantors should be properly explained by credit institutions about the content of the obligation assumed by the guarantor, which often places a heavy burden on the guarantor.

Keywords: suretyship, obligation, personal, guarantee, accessory.

"In civil circulation, suretyship is one of the most common means of securing the performance of an obligation. Its peculiarity lies in the fact that, according to the suretyship, "the surety undertakes to be liable to the creditor for the failure to fulfill the obligation assumed by a third party. Unlike the collateral security measure, the suretyship does not grant the creditor the right to any preferential satisfaction over any specific property of the surety, but by virtue of the suretyship, the creditor, along with the main claim against the debtor, also acquires an additional obligation-legal claim against the surety. Accordingly, unlike collateral security, the suretyship appears as a means of personal security, in which the solvency of the surety is of decisive importance in ensuring the creditor's interest in performance. Unlike collateral security, in the case of suretyship, the guarantor's liability is not limited to any specific object or objects, but within the scope of the suretyship, the creditor can apply to the entire property of the guarantor to satisfy his claim."¹

Thus, "Guarantee represents a means of securing a claim by legal, contractual means. When lending funds, the creditor, whether it is an individual or a legal entity, a credit institution, often resorts to the use of an additional means of security, that is, a surety."² A suretyship is a unilateral, consensual and causal agreement involving the debtor, the surety, and the creditor. The purpose of a suretyship agreement is to

personally secure the obligation assumed by the debtor to the creditor.³

"Banks do not rely solely on a mortgage or collateral when granting a loan, and they also require the involvement of relatives and family members in fulfilling the borrower's obligations."⁴

"The value of a surety as a means of security is determined by the financial situation of the guarantor."⁵ Therefore, family members must be solvent and meet the requirements set by the credit organization.

"A surety may be entered into to ensure the performance of any contract. The law does not provide for any restrictions regarding suretyship; therefore, based on the principle of private autonomy and freedom of will of the parties, the parties are free to enter into a suretyship to secure both contractual and legal obligations - legal relations. As a rule, in practice, a suretyship is entered into to ensure the performance of a monetary obligation"⁶.

"A surety, like a mortgage and a pledge, is an accessory means of security, it is entirely dependent on the main debt (claim)."⁷ According to Article 893 of the Civil Code of Georgia, "the existence of a corresponding principal obligation is determined for the obligation of a surety."⁸ If the underlying right did not arise due to the invalidity of the transaction or other grounds, the suretyship is not considered to have arisen; if the underlying right is subsequently terminated, this

¹Collective of authors, Contract Law, Textbook for Law Schools, "Meridian", 2014. p. 546

²Gabisonia Z. Banking Law, "World of Lawyers", 2015, p. 185

³Lipartia N, "Management and Legal Consequences of Beneficiary Claims Under Bank Guarantees", Doctoral Thesis. 2018, pp. 53-55

⁴Shengelia R. Shengelia E. Fundamentals of Banking Law, "Law", 2014, p. 428

⁵ Chanturia L. Credit Security Law, "Sam,Artali", 2012, p. 182

⁶ Collective of authors, Contract Law, Textbook for Law Schools, "Meridian", 2014, pp. 546-547

⁷ Chanturia L. Credit Security Law, "Sam,Artali", 2012, p. 183

⁸ Civil Code of Georgia, June 26, 1997, Article 893

automatically results in the termination of the suretyship without any additional agreement or communication between the parties.

Despite the imperative requirement of the law, “the strict principle of the accessory nature of suretyship is somehow “softened” by allowing the possibility of using suretyship to secure future and contingent obligations.”⁹

The parties may also agree to secure future and contingent obligations. However, future and contingent obligations do not exist until a specific term or condition has occurred, although the suretyship agreement is still valid, and the right arising from the suretyship agreement does not arise until the term or condition has occurred. In addition, despite its accessory nature, the surety's obligation is not increased by the transaction that the principal debtor enters into after the conclusion of the suretyship agreement.

In order for a suretyship to arise, it is necessary to conclude an agreement between the creditor and the sureties. The participation of the debtor in the conclusion of the aforementioned agreement is not mandatory, although the agreement may be concluded tripartitely, namely with the participation of the debtor, the creditor and the surety.

Although, “the suretyship is closely related to the secured claim and does not exist without it, the change in the claim does not automatically affect the scope of the surety's liability. In particular, according to the 2nd sentence of Article 893 of the Civil Code of Georgia, the surety's liability shall not increase with a transaction concluded by the principal debtor after the suretyship has been taken and shall not extend to the relations arising from this transaction. However. It is worth noting that in practice, banks abuse their authority and in most cases, in their agreements, which are of a template type and only the names of the debtor and the guarantor change, we often find a note that “the guarantor is liable for all obligations of the debtor”¹⁰, which in turn contradicts the 2nd sentence of Article 893 of the Civil Code of Georgia, which states that “the guarantor's obligation shall not increase with a transaction concluded by the principal debtor after the guarantor has been accepted and shall not extend to relations arising from this transaction”.

Also, in practice, there are frequent cases when guarantors cannot understand the content of the aforementioned agreement, which has repeatedly harmed the guarantor in the event of the debtor's failure to fulfill his obligation.¹¹

According to Article 905 of the Civil Code of Georgia, in the event of the guarantor satisfying the creditor, the creditor's claim against the principal debtor is transferred to him. The principal debtor's claims arising from the legal relationship between him and the guarantor remain unaffected. “The often disputed issue of whether the principal claim actually existed can be clarified by the guarantor in a regressive action brought

against the creditor (as long as the latter, of course, bears the burden of proof) in the process of bringing a regressive action. If, according to the substantive law governing the guarantor, the creditor has unlawfully accepted the performance of the obligation, then not only the guarantor, but also the principal debtor, on the basis of the security terms concluded with the creditor, has the right to claim his own recourse, which is primarily aimed at transferring the illegally paid amount to the guarantor. If the expenses incurred by the surety during the consideration of the recourse claim have already been reimbursed by the principal debtor, then the latter may demand the performance of the requested surety against him, contrary to the terms of the contract. In the process of relations between the principal debtor and the creditor, as well as in the process of bringing a recourse claim against the creditor by the surety, all material prerequisites for the occurrence of the circumstances of the surety's liability must be established, the existence of which must also be proven by the creditor.¹²

There is a regressive claim of the surety between the surety and the principal debtor, the realization of which is possible under the law through the legal transfer of the claim.

According to the German Civil Code, “under a suretyship agreement, the surety undertakes an obligation to stand as surety for a third party creditor for the performance of the third party's obligation. Suretyship can also be given for future and contingent obligations. In general, a suretyship is a typical means of personal security for credit (as opposed to collateral security for credit, such as, for example, mortgage, pledge, transfer of ownership for the purpose of security). The surety undertakes an obligation to stand as surety for the (secured) debt of another person.”¹³

French civil law does not impose any special requirements on the form of a suretyship; the form of a suretyship is subject to the general norms of the transaction. A suretyship is permitted even without the debtor's request, however, if the debtor presents the suretyship to the creditor, then the surety must be capable of acting, must have sufficient property and a place of residence in the territorial unit of the court of appeal where the suretyship is issued. It is noteworthy that the norms of French private law are based on the norms of French private law; in fact, the institution of suretyship in Japanese private law, as well as the norms of the Belgian Civil Code, are the result of the reception of the French Civil Code in relation to the suretyship agreement. Here, too, the suretyship is of an accessory nature.

The norms of the Italian Civil Code regarding suretyship are in fact identical to those of German and French law. Here too, “the law does not contain provisions on the form of suretyship; it is likely that general provisions on the form of the transaction apply to it as well. Italian law allows for the existence of

⁹<http://www.gccc.ge/>

¹⁰ Chanturia L. Credit Security Law, "Sam,Artali", 2012, p. 184

¹¹ See, Decision of the Civil Cases Chamber of the Supreme Court, Case No. AS-372-2023. October 6. Tbilisi.

¹² Kropholer I, German Civil Code, Educational Commentary, GIZ, Tbilisi 2014, p. 566

¹³ Kropholer I, German Civil Code, Educational Commentary, GIZ, Tbilisi 2014, p. 565

suretyship in relation to future and contingent obligations, and also extends to all accessory obligations related to the main obligation. In Italian private law, suretyship implies joint and several liability, unless otherwise stipulated in the suretyship agreement. The Austrian private law describes the suretyship agreement in detail. "In the case of a simple suretyship, the creditor may file a claim against the surety after the main debtor has failed to fulfill his obligation and has filed a claim against him and has not received appropriate satisfaction. In the case of a joint and several suretyship, the creditor has the choice of whom to address with the claim, the original debtor or the guarantors.

In Swiss civil law, the institution of suretyship largely coincides with the norms in the German Civil Code. "For all types of use of suretyship, it is mandatory to comply with the written form, which must specify the scope of the suretyship and the maximum amount. The joint liability of the co-sureties is determined to the creditor within the limits of the share assumed by them. In the case of a fixed-term suretyship, the guarantors are only released from liability when the creditor does not file a claim against the principal debtor within four weeks after the expiration of the term of the suretyship. In the case of a perpetual surety, the surety may, upon the due date for the performance of the principal debtor's obligation, require the creditor to file his claim with the court within four weeks and to conduct the case against him without significant delay.¹⁴

Thus, the discussion of suretyship as a means of personal security of a claim in the private law legislation of Georgia and foreign countries has revealed the similarities and differences that characterize this institution in the countries of continental Europe and the Anglo-American legal system. It is evident that suretyship, along with other means of securing a claim, in all countries creates a solid foundation for protecting and increasing the

stability of the economic turnover of society and ensuring its continuous development.

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¹⁴ Svanadze N, "Guarantee as a Means of Ensuring the Fulfillment of Obligations under the Civil Legislation of Foreign Countries", Journal "Law" #1-2, 2004, p. 39.